

LONGITUDINAL EDUCATIONAL ACHIEVEMENTS: REDUCING INEQUALITIES

LEARN

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Authors Doris Hanappi

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report brings together efforts to map and interpret the evidence base on educational inequalities, focusing on socioeconomic status, ethnic background, and peer context as key drivers of educational outcomes. The report includes a meta-review, a systematic review, and a case study from the Netherlands, each shedding light on the mechanisms driving disparities in education and surfacing a strong evidence base to guide policy strategies within the Horizon project LEARN. The evidence formats in this report will be made publicly available on [Zenodo](#), the [EU LEARN website](#) and the [LEARN evidence platform](#).

The meta-review in LEARN BRIEF 01/24 and LEARN YELLOW PAPER 01/24 synthesizes 29 literature reviews (1,950 studies from 2019-2024) on educational inequalities related to socioeconomic disadvantage. Drawing on insights from social sciences and humanities, it identifies major evidence gaps, proposing an interdisciplinary framework to address inequality phases and mechanisms. The review emphasizes evidence-based policies that bridge social and educational sectors, with five guiding questions for future research and policy.

The systematic review in LEARN BRIEF 02/24 analyses 27 studies (2007-2020) on biases in teacher recommendations for student tracking. It finds that students from disadvantaged socioeconomic and ethnic backgrounds often face biases, shaped by student and parent characteristics, teacher attitudes, and institutional policies, which can limit their educational opportunities. The review calls for targeted teacher training and institutional reforms to support equitable tracking practices.

The Dutch case study in LEARN BRIEF 03/24 explores peer influence on secondary school choice, analysing data from over 600,000 students transitioning from primary school between 2014 and 2019. In the Netherlands, where school choice is mostly unrestricted by geography, findings reveal that students from disadvantaged backgrounds often prioritize attending school with familiar peers, reflecting limited parental guidance and greater autonomy in school choices among low SES students. This peer effect underscores how peer networks shape school transitions and may unintentionally reinforce inequalities, despite broader access policies.

Together, these studies provide actionable insights for policymakers, emphasizing the importance of cross-sector policies to address socioeconomic inequalities, reforms to mitigate biases in teacher tracking, and inclusive school choice policies that account for peer influence. These findings underscore the complexity of educational inequality and the need for a coordinated EU response that fosters more inclusive and equitable educational systems across Europe.

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LEARN BRIEF 02: Reviewing the Evidence on the SES Gradient in Tracking Decisions

How Context and Institutions Can Cultivate Fair Education Pathways

Compiled by Doris Hanappi, from an original document (Are tracking recommendations biased? A review of teachers' role in the creation of inequalities in tracking decisions) by Anatolia Batruch, Sara Geven, Emma Kessenich, Herman G. van de Werfhorst.

Funding Acknowledgement

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1 ABOUT THE LEARN BRIEF

Imagine two students: Maria, from a low socio-economic status (SES) household, and Alex, from a high SES household. Despite having similar academic performance, their educational pathways may look very different. Studies show that Alex is more likely to receive teacher recommendations for advanced tracks, while Maria is more often directed toward less challenging options. This scenario reflects a broader trend: teacher judgments often extend beyond academic performance, with a meta-analysis of 73 studies showing that over 40% of the variance in teacher judgments can be attributed to non-academic factors (Südkamp, Kaiser, & Möller, 2012).

Addressing this issue, a research team affiliated to the EU Horizon Project LEARN undertook a comprehensive review to assess biases in teacher track recommendations, particularly against students from disadvantaged socio-economic and ethnic backgrounds. Researchers examined the sources of these biases, classifying them into student-parent, teacher, and contextual factors to understand how these influences interact with SES and ethnicity in shaping teacher recommendations. These findings, now available in detail, offer a critical foundation for policies aimed at promoting fairness in educational pathways.

2 ABOUT THIS SYSTEMATIC REVIEW

A systematic review of 27 quantitative studies published between 2007 and 2020 examined whether students' socio-economic and ethnic backgrounds influence teachers' tracking recommendations and identified factors contributing to any observed biases. Tracking recommendations refer to teachers' placement of students into

ability groups, which can shape educational opportunities. In this study, biases are defined as systematic differences in recommendations for equally performing students from different socio-economic or ethnic backgrounds.

The review analysed studies to understand how social and ethnic backgrounds impact teacher tracking and examined factors potentially driving these biases. These factors were categorized into three types: 1) individual student and parent characteristics like student school behaviour and attitudes, parent involvement and aspirations, 2) teacher-related characteristics like student-teacher relationship, teacher stereotypes and prejudices, and 3) contextual factors like institutional or school-specific conditions.

This review provides a comprehensive view of the socio-economic and ethnic biases in teacher recommendations, underscoring the role of institutional factors and offering a basis for policies to support fairer educational pathways.

3 KEY FINDINGS

3.1. Tracking Titled

Students from Low-SES Backgrounds Face Lower Track Recommendations Despite Comparable Performance

Evidence across 19 studies consistently shows a bias favouring students from high socio-economic status (SES) backgrounds. For instance, in France and the Netherlands, high-SES students are frequently recommended for advanced tracks over equally performing low-SES peers (Barg, 2013; Timmermans et al., 2015). Even when controlling for performance metrics like test scores and grades, students from lower SES backgrounds tend to receive lower track recommendations. In a three-country experimental design, teachers also had

lower expectations about low-SES students. Importantly, earlier performance was a major predictor of teacher expectations particularly in tracked systems, leading to self-fulfilling prophecies (Geven et al. 2021). However, an observational study in Southern Germany using parental occupational status as a measure of SES found no significant SES bias in teacher track recommendations when parental reports on the student's home learning environment were included (Niklas & Schneider, 2017). This suggests that higher SES households may provide a more supportive environment for learning and development, which plays a critical role in shaping teacher recommendations.

3.2. Mixed Signals

Inconsistent Evidence for Ethnic Bias in Teacher Track Recommendations

Among 24 studies investigating ethnic or migration-related biases in teacher track recommendations, results are varied. Nine studies suggest a bias against students from migration or ethnic minority backgrounds, while six studies find no evidence of bias, and another six indicate a possible bias in favour of these students. Additionally, two studies report less accurate recommendations for students with migration backgrounds, which may reflect either positive or negative biases depending on the context (Glock et al., 2015; Pit-ten Cate et al., 2016).

These mixed results may be attributed to variations in study design, the inclusion of socio-economic factors, and differing methods for measuring ethnicity or migration background. While observational studies typically use country of birth or parental origin, experimental studies often rely on indirect indicators, such as student names or language spoken at home, which may influence findings. This diversity in

methods highlights the need for standardized approaches in future research to more accurately assess the role of ethnic and migration background in teacher recommendations.

3.3. SES and Ethnic Biases Persist

Students' Behaviour and Home Shape Recommendations, But Bias Persists

While student behaviour, effort, and motivation positively influence teacher track recommendations, these factors do not eliminate SES and ethnic biases. Studies from Luxembourg and Germany show that teachers recommend higher tracks for students they perceive as hardworking. However, even when controlling for behaviour and other factors like parental involvement and teacher expectations, biases linked to socio-economic status and ethnicity continue to affect recommendations.

Nine studies link the home environment, including parental support, school involvement, and aspirations, to higher teacher track recommendations. For instance, in France and Germany, teachers tend to recommend higher tracks for students whose parents are actively involved in school activities or perceived as supportive in their child's learning (Barg, 2013; Krolak-Schwerdt et al., 2018). Similarly, Dutch studies suggest that students from homes that encourage learning and curiosity receive more favourable recommendations (Driessen et al., 2008).

Teachers often hold positive perceptions of school-involved parents, typically associated with advantaged backgrounds, which may partially explain SES biases in tracking. Some research also suggests that middle- and upper-SES parents, more likely to advocate for their child, indirectly influence teachers to provide higher track recommendations (Barg, 2015). However,

while parental involvement and aspirations relate to favourable tracking outcomes, studies indicate that these factors do not fully account for SES biases, suggesting that socio-economic disparities in recommendations persist despite controlling for the home environment.

3.4. Shifting the Focus

Tackling Bias Through Institutional Change

Preliminary but promising evidence suggests that institutional features, particularly those related to accountability and selection, may amplify SES biases in teacher track recommendations. For instance, studies indicate that accountability structures impact teachers' decision-making processes, with less accountability leading to greater susceptibility to bias. In an experimental study by Glock et al. (2012), teachers made tracking recommendations under varying levels of accountability. When teachers were merely advising a colleague without responsibility for the final decision, biases linked to student nationality emerged. However, when teachers were held accountable to a decision-making council, these biases diminished, highlighting how institutional accountability can shape and potentially reduce biases.

Further emphasizing institutional impact, Pit-ten Cate et al. (2016) found that increasing accountability by prompting teachers to reflect on their decision accuracy improved tracking outcomes for ethnic minority students. However, accuracy improvements over time were more pronounced for majority students, indicating that accountability measures may not fully mitigate bias, particularly when related to SES and ethnic background.

Another study by Batruch et al. (2019) examined how a school's primary function—whether to "select" or

"educate" students—influences tracking recommendations. Results showed that SES biases were heightened in a selection-oriented context, where high-SES students were deemed more suitable for advanced tracks, while low-SES students were more likely placed in lower tracks. In contrast, when the focus shifted to an educational function aimed at supporting all students, SES-related disparities in recommendations were smaller.

These findings suggest that institutional emphasis on selection versus support can shape the SES gradient in tracking decisions, with selection-focused environments likely reinforcing biases. Together, these studies highlight the need for educational policies that prioritize supportive, educational frameworks over selective mechanisms to reduce SES-related inequalities in teacher recommendations.

4 IMPLICATIONS – THE OPPORTUNITY

This section outlines the main implications of these findings for the evidence-informed policy-design, and the opportunities to build on, and drive forward the extension of evidence generation and the evaluation of existing evidence.

4.1. Exploring Institutional and Contextual Influences on Biases

Current research highlights the persistence of socio-economic (SES) and ethnic biases in teacher track recommendations, yet few studies have investigated the mechanisms underlying these biases. Individual characteristics, such as student behaviour and parental involvement, do not fully explain the bias observed in recommendations. Moreover, studies indicate significant variation in biases across different teachers and schools,

suggesting that the broader educational context may play a crucial role. To address this gap, future research should examine how contextual factors—like institutional policies and school environments— influence biases. Educational institutions, as cultural contexts, have the potential to shape teacher behaviours and contribute to reducing social inequalities, making them a promising focus for intervention.

4.2. Targeting Institutional Features for Policy Intervention

Understanding how national and school-level policies impact teacher recommendations could inform targeted interventions to reduce bias. For instance, non-binding recommendations, such as those in parts of Germany and Belgium, may lower teacher accountability and, in turn, amplify biases. Conversely, contexts with a high degree of school autonomy might allow for standardized guidelines and teacher collaboration that help mitigate biases. Cross-national studies also suggest that policy frameworks, such as those supporting disadvantaged students, can influence teacher attitudes and potentially reduce bias.

4.3. Developing Practical, Contextual Interventions

Research from non-educational settings offers insights into interventions that could apply to schools. Studies show that blinding decision-makers to social categories, using clear, pre-defined criteria, and involving third-party evaluators can reduce biases in evaluations. Applying these strategies in educational settings could involve anonymizing student records for track recommendations or requiring teachers to base recommendations on standardized, objective criteria. These low-cost, context-based interventions offer promising avenues for reducing SES and ethnic biases in teacher recommendations,

thereby supporting more equitable student outcomes.

5 RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1. Policy Recommendations

Implement **Standardized Criteria** for Track Recommendations

To reduce SES and ethnic biases in track recommendations, educational policymakers should consider developing standardized, objective criteria for track placements. By providing clear guidelines that focus on measurable competencies, institutions can help limit subjective factors in decision-making, making recommendations more equitable across socio-economic groups.

Increase **Accountability Measures** in Track Decision Processes

Introducing accountability structures, such as oversight councils or peer reviews for tracking decisions, could improve the fairness of teacher recommendations. Research indicates that accountability can reduce the expression of biases by ensuring that teachers are more deliberate and reflective in their recommendations, especially in contexts where biases against low-SES students have been observed.

Encourage **School-Level Policies** that Emphasize **Educational Support** Over Selection

Policies that shift the focus from selecting high-performing students to providing support for all can reduce SES-based disparities in tracking. Schools that prioritize educational support over selective categorization are likely to promote more inclusive and equitable pathways, particularly for students from disadvantaged backgrounds.

5.2. Research Recommendations

Examine the **Role of Contextual and Institutional Factors** in Bias

Researchers should further investigate how national and school-level institutional characteristics shape teacher biases in tracking. Cross-country studies, for instance, could provide insights into how varying educational structures, such as binding versus non-binding recommendations, influence the consistency and fairness of teacher judgments. In addition, longitudinal studies should be designed to assess long-term impacts of such recommendations on educational pathways, attainment, entry into the labour market, and overall development and well-being.

Investigate the Impact of **Accountability Mechanisms** on Teacher Tracking Decision Processes

Introducing accountability structures, such as oversight councils or peer reviews for tracking decisions, could improve the fairness of teacher recommendations and contribute to a culture of support and opportunity for learning. Research should assess how and to what extent accountability can reduce the expression of biases by ensuring that teachers are more deliberate and reflective in their recommendations, fostering an environment that prioritizes equitable opportunities for all students, especially those from disadvantaged backgrounds.

Explore **Longitudinal Effects** of Institutional Interventions on Bias

Long-term studies are needed to understand the sustained impact of institutional interventions, such as standardized criteria and accountability frameworks, on reducing SES and ethnic biases. Tracking these interventions over time would provide valuable data on the

persistence of bias and the conditions that support lasting changes in teacher decision-making.

6 CONCLUSIONS

This policy brief highlights the complex and enduring impact of socio-economic status (SES) and ethnic biases in teacher tracking recommendations, shedding light on how institutional and contextual factors can influence these decisions. Evidence suggests that, while individual characteristics like student behaviour and parental involvement affect track recommendations, they do not fully explain the persistent SES and ethnic disparities observed across educational systems. Rather, the institutional context—such as accountability measures, selection versus educational support emphasis, and standardized criteria—plays a critical role in either reinforcing or mitigating these biases.

To promote fair educational pathways, it is essential to prioritize policies that encourage accountability and focus on support over selection. Such initiatives can foster a culture of equity, enabling all students, regardless of their socio-economic or ethnic backgrounds, to have equal opportunities for advancement. Moving forward, research must deepen its focus on the mechanisms through which institutional contexts shape teacher decisions and explore interventions that can sustain bias reduction over time.

To create a more inclusive and equitable education system, policymakers must shift the emphasis from individual traits to institutional practices that actively promote fairness in teacher recommendations. By implementing accountability measures, standardized criteria, and policies that prioritize educational support over selection, educational systems can ensure that

students' academic pathways reflect their true abilities and potential—not the limitations imposed by socio-economic or ethnic biases.

This call to action underscores the responsibility of educational institutions to dismantle systemic barriers and foster learning environments where every student has an equal opportunity to thrive.

Now is the time for concrete policy initiatives that will move us closer to a future where tracking decisions empower all students, regardless of background, to reach their fullest potential.

7 REFERENCES

- Adams, G., Biernat, M., Branscombe, N. R., Crandall, C. S., & Wrightsman, L. S. (2008). Beyond prejudice: Toward a sociocultural psychology of racism and oppression. In G. Adams, M. Biernat, N. R. Branscombe, C. S. Crandall, & L. S. Wrightsman (Eds.), *Commemorating Brown: The social psychology of racism and discrimination* (pp. 215e246). Washington, DC: American Psychological Association.
<https://doi.org/10.1037/11681-012>
- Barg, K. (2013). The influence of students' social background and parental involvement on teachers' school track choices: reasons and consequences. *European Sociological Review*, 29(3), 565-579.
<https://www.jstor.org/stable/24479995>
- Batruch, A., Autin, F., Bataillard, F., & Butera, F. (2019). School selection and the social class divide: How tracking contributes to the reproduction of inequalities. *Personality and Social Psychology Bulletin*, 45(3), 477e490.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/0146167218791804>
- Driessen, G., Slegers, P., & Smit, F. (2008). The transition from primary to secondary education: Meritocracy and ethnicity. *European Sociological Review*, 24(4), 527e542.
<https://doi.org/10.1093/esr/jcn018>
- Geven, S., Wiborg, Ø. N., Fish, R. E., & van de Werfhorst, H. G. (2021). How teachers form educational expectations for students: A comparative factorial survey experiment in three institutional contexts. *Social Science Research*, 102599.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssresearch.2021.102599>
- Glock, S., Krolak-Schwerdt, S., & Pit-ten Cate, I. M. (2015). Are school placement recommendations accurate? The effect of students' ethnicity on teachers' judgments and recognition memory. *European Journal of Psychology of Education*, 30(2), 169e188. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10212-014-0237-2>
- Krolak-Schwerdt, S., Hörstermann, T., Glock, S., & Böhmer, I. (2018). Teachers' assessments of students' achievements: The ecological validity of studies using case vignettes. *The Journal of Experimental Education*, 86(4), 515e529.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/00220973.2017.1370686>
- Niklas, F., & Schneider, W. (2017). Home learning environment and development of child competencies from kindergarten until the end of elementary school. *Contemporary Educational Psychology*, 49, 263e274.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cedpsych.2017.03.006>
- Pit-ten Cate, I. M., Krolak-Schwerdt, S., & Glock, S. (2016). Accuracy of teachers' tracking decisions: Short-and long-term effects of accountability. *European Journal of Psychology of Education*, 31(2), 225e243. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10212-015-0259-4>

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Südkamp, A., Kaiser, J., & Möller, J. (2012). Accuracy of teachers' judgments of students' academic achievement: A meta-analysis. American Psychological Association.

<https://doi.org/10.1037/a0027627>

LEARN BRIEF 03: Unseen Currents: How Peer Influence Shapes School Choices and Inequality in Dutch Education

Compiled by Dieuwke Zwier and Doris Hanappi, from an original document (Let's stick together: Peer effects in secondary school choice and variations by student socio-economic background) by Dieuwke Zwier, Sara Geven, Thijs Bol and Herman G. van de Werfhorst for EU LEARN.

Funding Acknowledgement

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1 ABOUT THE LEARN BRIEF

Socioeconomic inequality in education is a complex, multi-layered challenge, and the EU Horizon Project LEARN, led by the University of Helsinki, set out to address this through mapping of existing research across all phases of student development to highlight untapped opportunities for understanding how socioeconomic disparities arise. While existing theories offer robust much of the current research focuses narrowly on family-level influences, overlooking broader contextual factors. These overlooked factors—such as peer networks, school environments, and neighbourhood conditions—play a significant role in shaping the socioeconomic gradient in educational inequality. Understanding these contextual factors is essential for a more comprehensive understanding of socioeconomic inequality in education.

One area that remains underexplored is the role of the peer context during educational transitions. This LEARN brief presents a recent study on peer effects in secondary school choice from one of the LEARN countries, the Netherlands. The full study is published in a peer-reviewed article, accessible [here](#).

2 ABOUT THIS CASE STUDY

The role of the peer context in (secondary) school choice has been understudied, with school choice largely attributed to family decisions. This study shifts the focus to investigate whether students from the same primary school cluster into the same secondary school, beyond just the popularity of specific secondary schools in primary schools. Additionally, it examined whether students from disadvantaged socioeconomic backgrounds, who often have comparatively fewer educational resources at home and greater autonomy in educational decisions, are more

susceptible to peer influence during this transition.

Using comprehensive administrative data from over 600,000 Dutch students transitioning from primary to secondary school between 2014 and 2019, the study provides unique insights. The Netherlands offers an intriguing case for this analysis, as school choice is relatively one (little limited financial and geographical constraints): virtually all schools are publicly funded, and students are not geographically bound by school catchment areas or school districts. This allows researchers to explore the influence of familiar peers on school choice without geographical or financial restrictions. The study used geospatial and ability tracking data to identify all schools relatively close to each student's home they are eligible to attend. It statistically compared the features of the school students enrolled in with those of plausible alternatives that were not chosen. The comparisons offer insights into the weight placed on familiar peer presence in secondary school, alongside with other school attributes such as proximity, perceived school quality, and composition.

3 KEY FINDINGS

3.1. School Choice is a Social Decision

Though underdeveloped in existing research, this study demonstrates that secondary school choice is fundamentally a social decision, influenced by peer networks, rather than just family context. Families are more likely to choose a secondary school if a substantial share of a student's primary school peers also enrol there. This peer effect stands independently of other factors, such as proximity, perceived school quality, school demographics, and other additional (unobserved) attributes that may make certain secondary schools more or less

popular among students from a given primary school.

3.2. SES Gradient in Susceptibility to Peer Influence

This tendency to follow primary school peers across educational transitions is slightly more pronounced among students whose parents did not complete post-secondary or higher education. Other research highlights socioeconomic disparities in the knowledge needed to navigate educational trajectories (Lareau, 2015; Forster & Van de Werfhorst, 2020). The peer context may partially compensate for the relatively fewer educational resources available to disadvantaged students at home. Related to this, disadvantaged students may experience more autonomy in educational decisions than their advantaged counterparts, whose parents play a more decisive role. Understanding socioeconomic differences in the magnitude of peer effects is essential for broader discussions on the impact of social networks on inequality in education and other domains (Chetty et al., 2020; DiMaggio & Garip, 2012).

4 IMPLICATIONS – THE OPPORTUNITY

The Dutch context offers a unique and insightful case study for understanding school choice dynamics in Europe, allowing researchers and policy makers to observe and account for peer influences on educational transitions without the typical financial or geographic constraints that limit school choice elsewhere. This section outlines the main implications of these findings for the educational evidence base, highlighting opportunities to expand, advance, and rigorously evaluate both new and existing evidence.

4.1. Impact of Context in Educational Decision-making

To fully understand (socioeconomic disparities in) school choice – and educational decision-making more broadly – it is essential to go beyond examining family-level choice processes in isolation and instead consider peers and other contextual influences. Recognizing these contextual influences can enhance policies aimed at reducing school segregation. Peer effects in school choice mean that segregation patterns established in primary schools may persist or even intensify in later educational stages. Effective Desegregation policies should be designed with closer attention to such interdependencies across educational stages resulting from peer dynamics.

4.2. Socioeconomic Variations in Contextual Influences

The peer or school environment may influence children's educational decisions differently depending on their socioeconomic background, relative educational achievement, and other characteristics. The study employed geospatial and ability tracking data to evaluate each student's accessible school options and compared the characteristics of the chosen schools with plausible alternatives. A deeper understanding of underlying mechanisms is needed to identify which types of decisions and which student subgroups are most susceptible to peer influence.

Socioeconomic background significantly shapes how students are influenced by their peers and school environments when making educational decisions. Students from different socioeconomic backgrounds often have access to varying resources, support systems, and information networks, which affects how they interpret and act on peer influences. For instance,

students from higher socioeconomic backgrounds may have parents who actively guide them through educational choices, providing advice and resources that reduce reliance on peers. In contrast, students from lower socioeconomic backgrounds may have less parental involvement or fewer resources, making peer networks more influential in shaping their educational paths.

In addition, students with different levels of academic achievement or confidence in their abilities may interpret peer behaviours and choices differently. For example, high-achieving students may be more inclined to follow peers who choose academically rigorous schools or programs, while students with lower academic confidence might be more sensitive to peer influence when it comes to decisions that prioritize familiarity and social comfort. This dynamic suggests that the impact of contextual factors like peer influence varies not only by socioeconomic background but also by academic identity and self-perception.

5 RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1. Research Recommendations

Study the **Role of Peers in Educational Transitions**

Increase investment in targeted research to explore the multifaceted role of peers in educational transitions. Peers can have different, sometimes even contrasting functions in educational decision-making:

(1) they may provide emotional support as students transition to new academic environments; (2) they can serve as valuable sources of information, helping students make informed decisions; (3) they act as social reference points, shaping educational aspirations through comparison; and (4) they may exert normative pressure, encouraging students

to align their aspirations or choices with group expectations (see Rosenqvist & Brandén, 2024). Research should further assess how various peer groups (e.g., friends, classmates, desk mates) affect educational decisions to better understand these underlying mechanisms of peer influence.

Examine **Heterogeneous Peer Effects to Address Inequality**

Peer effects are crucial to understanding social inequality in education since students do not face the same peer context in school (Engzell & Raabe, 2023; Zwier & Geven, 2023), nor are they equally susceptible to peer influence. While the peer context can have a compensatory function for disadvantaged students, it can also exacerbate social inequality if schools and networks are segregated, or more advantaged families are better able to reap their educational benefits. Rather than focusing on average peer effects, research should examine which subgroups of students, under what conditions, are most susceptible to peer influence in education.

Integrate Insights on **Peer Effects in Segregation Research**

Understanding how peer dynamics influence school choice and contribute to segregation requires innovative research approaches, as traditional methods struggle to account for the feedback loops that reinforce these patterns. For example, when students cluster with peers in school transitions, it can perpetuate segregation over time, making it difficult to separate cause and effect.

5.2. Policy Recommendations

Consider **Interdependencies Across Educational Stages** in Desegregation Policies

School segregation can feed into later educational stages through peer effects in school choice. Recognising these interdependencies is essential for developing effective policies to address school segregation based on socioeconomic and/or ethnic background.

Support (Disadvantaged) Students in Educational Transitions

Providing centralized and accessible information, such as through guided school tours or similar initiatives, can help address long-standing school reputations and transform local norms around "appropriate" school choices. A key challenge is that these interventions reach and resonate with all families, especially those in disadvantaged groups. Tailored strategies, such as targeted outreach, multilingual resources, or personalized guidance, may be necessary to effectively engage these students and families, ensuring they have the tools and confidence to explore diverse and high-quality educational opportunities.

6 CONCLUSIONS

This case study from the Netherlands focuses on the role of peers in school choice, offering valuable insights into an understudied contextual factor linked to social inequality in education. Large-scale quantitative analyses of data from over 600,000 Dutch students transitioning to secondary school in the period 2014-2019 reveal that primary school peers tend to "cluster" in the same secondary school, beyond the general popularity of schools. This pattern is slightly more pronounced among socioeconomically disadvantaged students.

These findings emphasize the pivotal role of peers in shaping educational decision-making. To better understand socioeconomic disparities in educational

trajectories, research should move beyond examining family-level choice processes in isolation and instead consider the impact of peers and other contextual influences. Further research into the mechanisms driving peer influence is warranted to explore how these dynamics operate. Furthermore, research should focus on socioeconomic variations in peer effects to evaluate how peer contexts either mitigate or exacerbate social inequalities in education.

The findings also highlight how secondary school segregation may be partly rooted in primary school through peer dynamics, reinforcing patterns of inequality over time. To address this, desegregation policies must carefully account for these interdependencies across educational stages. Designing (targeted) interventions that support students across all socioeconomic backgrounds is essential to promoting equality of opportunity in educational transitions for every learner.

7 REFERENCES

- Chetty, R., Jackson, M. O., Kuchler, T., Stroebel, J., Hendren, N., Fluegge, R. B., Gong, S., Gonzalez, F., Grondin, A., Jacob, M., Johnston, D., Koenen, M., Laguna-Muggenburg, E., Mudekereza, F., Rutter, T., Thor, N., Townsend, W., Zhang, R., Bailey, M., ... Wernerfelt, N. (2022). Social capital I: Measurement and associations with economic mobility. *Nature*, 608, 108–121. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-022-04996-4>
- DiMaggio, P., & Garip, F. (2012). Network effects and social inequality. *Annual Review of Sociology*, 38, 93–118. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.soc.012809.102545>
- Engzell, P., & Raabe, I. J. (2023). Within-school achievement sorting in comprehensive and tracked systems.

Sociology of Education, 96(4), 253–367.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/00380407231183952>

Lareau, A. (2015). Cultural knowledge and social inequality. *American Sociological Review*, 80(1), 1–27.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/0003122414565814>

Forster, A. G., & Van de Werfhorst, H. G. (2020). Navigating institutions: Parents' knowledge of the educational system and students' success in education. *European Sociological Review*, 36(1), 48–64.
<https://doi.org/10.1093/esr/jcz049>

Rosenqvist, E., & Brandén, M. (2024). School composition and academic decisions. *European Sociological Review*, jcae031.
<https://doi.org/10.1093/esr/jcae031>

Zwier, D., & Geven, S. (2023). Knowing me, knowing you: Socio-economic status and (segregation in) peer and parental networks in primary school. *Social Networks*, 74, 127–138.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.socnet.2023.03.003>